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Review Article

**CONGENITAL HYPOTHYROIDISM PREVALENCE
DIAGNOSIS AND OUTCOME IN SAUDI ARABIA**Hala M. Yousif¹, Rawan A. Alotaibi², Nada R. Almshhen²¹ Assistant Professor and Consultant Pathologist, Department of Pathology, College of Medicine, Taibah University, Medina, Saudi Arabia² Taibah College of Medicine, Taibah University, Medina, Saudi Arabia**Article Received:** September 2020 **Accepted:** September 2020 **Published:** October 2020**Abstract:**

Background: Congenital hypothyroidism (CH) is known as one of the most common preventable causes of mental retardation, with a worldwide prevalence of 1:3500–1:5000, and a prevalence in Saudi Arabia of 1:2500. CH is classified into primary or secondary hypothyroidism. Almost all infants with CH do not show clear clinical picture of hypothyroidism at birth, due to the beneficial effect of transplacental maternal thyroid hormone to the fetus. Early diagnosis is critical due to its role in brain growth through the first few months of life.

Objectives:

1. Determine the prevalence of congenital hypothyroidism in Saudi Arabia.
2. Identify the diagnostic criteria of congenital hypothyroidism.
3. Explore the outcome of congenital hypothyroidism.

Review of literature: A recent regional screening program was done in Saudi Arabia in 2011 revealed an analysis of 1,007,350 newborns, and showed CH in 306 indicating an incidence 1 in 3292. Evidences showed that age of starting Levothyroxine treatment dose, and severity of hypothyroidism each plays an important role in neurocognitive outcome.

Conclusion: The newborn screening for congenital hypothyroidism has been incorporated into neonatal screening programs. Studies from various regional programs in Saudi Arabia have revealed an incidence of 1 in 2500- 3500. Neurodevelopmental outcome generally is normal, if the diagnosis is made and treatment started within a few weeks of birth.

Keywords: Congenital, hypothyroidism, dyshormongogenesis, screening, Saudi Arabia, prevalence, Levothyroxine.

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INTRODUCTION:

Congenital hypothyroidism (CH) is known as one of the most common preventable causes of mental retardation, with a worldwide prevalence of 1:3500–1:5000, and a prevalence in Saudi Arabia of 1:2500⁽¹⁾. CH is classified into primary or secondary hypothyroidism. Primary congenital hypothyroidism is caused by defects of thyroid gland development (thyroid ectopia, hypoplasia, and aplasia) and dysmorphogenesis⁽²⁾. Secondary congenital hypothyroidism is a rare cause of hypothyroidism⁽³⁾ and refers to deficiency of thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH), due to either hypothalamic or pituitary dysfunction. Genetic causes of congenital hypothyroidism are rare, and results from mutations in thyrotropin-releasing hormone (TRH) gene, the TRH receptor⁽⁴⁾ or TSH⁽⁵⁾⁽⁶⁾.

Around 85% of CH are consequences from abnormalities in thyroid development⁽⁷⁾, the remaining 15% are defects in thyroid hormone synthesis which lead to thyroid dysmorphogenesis⁽⁸⁾.

Almost all infants with CH do not show clear clinical picture of hypothyroidism at birth, due to the beneficial effect of transplacental maternal thyroid hormone to the fetus. Clinical features will present in the first week of life and include increased sleeping time, poor feeding, constipation and hoarse cry. The most common signs are macroglossia and umbilical hernia. Further examination might show jaundice, a wide posterior fontanel and hypotonia⁽⁹⁾.

Early diagnosis is critical due to its role in brain growth through the first few months of life. Accessible data demonstrate that there is an exceptional prognosis for newborn with CH, if detected early and treated without delay⁽¹⁰⁾. This study aimed at providing the most relevant, updated information based on reviewing all existing evidence and latest findings about prevalence, diagnostic criteria and outcomes in infants with congenital hypothyroidism.

Review of literature**A. Epidemiology**

Prior to the beginning of newborns screening programs, the incidence of CH was in the range of 1:7,000 to 1:10,000⁽¹¹⁾. After the development of newborns screening programs, the incidence was reported to be in the range of 1:3,000 to 1:4,000⁽¹²⁾. Incidence varies by geographic location, as a French newborn screening program reported the incidence of CH to be 1:10,000 over a 20 years period⁽¹³⁾, while the Greek Cypriot population reported the incidence of 1:800 over an 11-year period⁽¹⁴⁾. The incidence in United States has increased from 1:4,094 in 1987 to 1:2,372 in 2002. A change in testing strategy could be one possible explanation for this increasing, as programs around the world switched from primary T4 follow up TSH approach to a primary TSH approach⁽¹⁵⁾.

A screening study was done in Saudi Arabia in 2002 demonstrated that 121,404 infants were screened over 15 years. The general rate of CH was 1:2759 live births with a female: male proportion of 1.8:1, their mean age at the onset of treatment in the screening program was 10.3 days⁽¹⁶⁾. Another regional screening program was done in Saudi Arabia in 2011 which was prepared and directed by nearby provincial councils and comprised of a pediatrician, laboratory technician, manager and social worker, that revealed an overall analysis of 1,007,350 newborns, and showed CH in 306 indicating an incidence 1 in 3292 (Table 1). The study obtained local variety in the incidence⁽¹⁷⁾⁽¹⁸⁾ because of numerous siblings in the family, and high consanguinity rate⁽¹⁹⁾. Of all newborn with CH who were screened, 147 infants showed CH, their thyroid gland was observed to be aplastic in 32 (21.8%), while in 62 (42.2%) thyroid gland was ectopic. Thyroid hormone dysmorphogenesis was observed in 53 babies (36%). Saudi Arabia revealed higher incidence than that reported from Europe and America⁽²⁰⁾⁽²¹⁾.

Table 1 Incidence of confirmed congenital hypothyroidism by the regional screening programs ⁽¹⁷⁾⁽¹⁸⁾

Region	Total # of newborn screened	No. of confirmed cases*	Incidence
1. Riyadh	283,647	83	1:3417
2. Qassim	75,024	21	1:3573
3. Hail	32,750	5	1:6550
4. Dammam	65,523	20	1:3276
5. Hassa	57,176	21	1:2723
6. Tabuk	31,431	10	1:3143
7. Madina	82,371	28	1:2942
8. Makkah	75,874	25	1:3035
9. Jeddah	40,659	10	1:4066
10. Taif	55,404	20	1:2770
11. Baha	23,128	3	1:7709
12. Assir	65,774	16	1:4110
13. Jizan	38,303	10	1:3830
14. Najran	30,810	22	1:1400
15. Hafer Al Batin	15,977	4	1:3994
16. Qurayat	9,360	2	1:4680
17. Jouf	7,920	1	1:7920
18. Arar	12,095	2	1:6047
19. Bisha	4,124	3	1:1374
TOTAL	1,007,350	306	1:3292

B. Diagnosis

Areas without newborn screening programs, diagnosis might be made after development of clinical picture of hypothyroidism. Considering the obstetric practice in Saudi Arabia where 95% of mothers deliver in hospitals, but with the majority being discharged within 24 hours, the program utilizes umbilical cord serum with thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH) to achieve the maximum diagnostic benefits. CH is mostly not a heritable disorder, and cases are mainly sporadic, but some pregnancies might be at higher risk based on a previous newborn with CH or a positive family history. Most cases are not familial and are found when routine ultrasonography reveals a fetal goiter ⁽²²⁾.

The test used for newborn screening program is blood from a heel-prick that is collected on special filter paper cards. The specimen is collected between two and five days of age. Screening programs are now using an initial TSH to detect CH instead of an initial T4 test, with a follow-up TSH test on infants below a

predefined T4 cut-off ⁽²³⁾.

Confirmatory serum is tested for TSH and either free T4 or total T4 combined with some measure of binding proteins. It is essential to compare the serum results and age-normal reference ranges. Confirmatory test is obtained in the first two weeks of life.

Other diagnostic studies might be used to determine the underlying etiology. Iodine-123 (I-123) and sodium pertechnetate 99 m (Tc99 m) are excellent for thyroid uptake and scan in neonates to minimize the radiation exposure. Radionuclide uptake and scanning is the most precise tests in distinguishing types of thyroid dysgenesis, e.g., an ectopic, hypoplastic, or aplastic thyroid gland ⁽²⁴⁾. Ultrasonography is accurate in confirming large gland suggestive of dyshormonogenesis, and true thyroid aplasia. Ultrasonography is not as accurate as radionuclide scan in confirming ectopic glands ⁽²⁵⁾. The amount of thyroid tissue is reflected by serum thyroglobulin levels, which are elevated with increased thyroid

activity, as when TSH is elevated. Maternal autoimmune thyroid disease is relatively common, as about 5% of women of reproductive age have either anti-thyroglobulin or thyroid peroxidase antibodies, as it crosses to the fetus and block TSH binding, therefore, interfering with fetal thyroid gland development and function⁽²⁶⁾. If an infant is born in an endemic area of iodine deficiency or excess, measurement of 24 hour urinary iodine may confirm the diagnosis. Genetic testing is considered mainly if other studies revealed a specific defect.

C. Outcome

The therapy goal is to achieve normal T4 level within 2 weeks and TSH within 1 month. The American Academy of Pediatrics recommended an initial starting dose of thyroxine of 10-15 ug/kg/day. However, a lower dose could be suggested. Serum T4 and TSH levels should be obtained in the first 3 years of life to make sure that serum T4 concentration stills in the normal range for age, and that the TSH stills controlled within the normal range (<5 mU/L).

Evidences revealed that age of onset of treatment, starting Levothyroxine treatment dose, and severity of hypothyroidism each plays a critical role in neurocognitive outcome. Ten studies compared the effect of different doses of Levothyroxine on psychometric outcome, 2 studies showed no effect, 6 studies showed a 12.3 higher IQ with higher starting doses, while 2 studies showed a 8.6 point higher IQ with lower starting doses⁽²⁷⁾⁽²⁸⁾. The decline of thyroid levels in the first two to three years after born lead to irreversible damage, this is because the normal brain development occurs in these years. However, decline the level after the first 3 years is reversible when corrected.

Starting Levothyroxine in the first 2 weeks of age at 9.5 microgram/kg has resulted in better outcomes compared to lower doses⁽²⁹⁾. There are minor differences between groups treated early and control groups in neuropsychological tests, intelligence and school achievement⁽³⁰⁾⁽³¹⁾⁽³²⁾⁽³³⁾. Residual defects include selective memory and sensorimotor defects and visuospatial processing impairment.

CONCLUSION:

Congenital hypothyroidism (CH) is the most widely recognized preventable cause for mental retardation. Newborn screening programs are the most ideal approach to identify infants with CH. Early diagnosis and starting treatment within a few weeks of birth will result in a normal neurodevelopmental outcome.

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Abbreviations:

(CH) Congenital hypothyroidism
(TSH) Thyroid-stimulating hormone
(TRH) Thyrotropin-releasing hormone

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